

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Authorship in mathematics

Short title	Authorship in mathematics
Long title	The 20 Highest Performing Authors in Mathematics Publish Third Most Articles But Have Comparably Low Bibliometrics
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Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Mathematics* is 2.9 on average with a maximum of 9 authors. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.1 per year in the

respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 3657$) were cited 8.2 times on average with a maximum of 357 citations.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA MATHEMATICS

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.1
Number of articles = 3657

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Mathematics*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers might not be visible. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016),
- the document types (articles or reviews),
- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).